

A Q -ANALOGUE OF GRANVILLE'S CONGRUENCE

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Abstract

In this paper, we establish a q -analogue of Granville's congruence as follows:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^k}{[k]_q} \equiv \frac{1 - x^p - (x; q)_p}{[p]_q} + x^p \frac{(p-1)(1-q)}{2} \pmod{[p]_q},$$

for any real number x and odd prime p . Here $[n]_q = 1 + q + q^2 + \dots + q^{n-1}$ and $(x; q)_n = (1-x)(1-xq) \dots (1-xq^{n-1})$.

1. Introduction

The harmonic numbers are given by

$$H_0 = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad H_n = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k} \quad \text{for } n \in \mathbb{Z}^+.$$

In [12], Wolstenholme discovered that for any prime number $p \geq 5$,

$$H_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

In [6], Lehmer showed that for any prime number $p \geq 3$,

$$H_{(p-1)/2} \equiv -2q_p(2) + pq_p^2(2) \pmod{p^2},$$

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where Fermat's quotient with base 2 is $q_p(2) = (2^{p-1} - 1)/p$.

The q -analogue of harmonic numbers H_n is given by

$$H_n(q) = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{q^k}{[k]_q},$$

where $[0]_q = 1$ and $[k]_q = (1 - q^k)/(1 - q) = 1 + q + q^2 + \dots + q^{k-1}$. It is easy to see that $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} [k]_q = k$.

The q -Pochhammer symbol is given by

$$(x; q)_0 = 1, \quad (x; q)_n = \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (1 - xq^k), \quad \text{for } n \geq 1.$$

For any $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, define the q -binomial coefficients by

$$\begin{bmatrix} n \\ m \end{bmatrix}_q = \frac{(q; q)_n}{(q; q)_m (q; q)_{n-m}},$$

if $n \geq m$, and if $n < m$, then $\begin{bmatrix} n \\ m \end{bmatrix}_q = 0$. It is clearly seen that

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \begin{bmatrix} n \\ m \end{bmatrix}_q = \binom{n}{m},$$

where $\binom{n}{m}$ is the usual binomial coefficient. The q -binomial coefficients satisfy the recurrence relation

$$\begin{bmatrix} n+1 \\ m \end{bmatrix}_q = q^m \begin{bmatrix} n \\ m \end{bmatrix}_q + \begin{bmatrix} n \\ m-1 \end{bmatrix}_q.$$

It is known that

$$\sum_{k=m}^n q^{k-m} \begin{bmatrix} k \\ m \end{bmatrix}_q = \begin{bmatrix} n+1 \\ m+1 \end{bmatrix}_q \tag{1}$$

and Rothe's formula (see [2]) is given by

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k q^{\binom{k}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} n \\ k \end{bmatrix}_q x^k = (x; q)_n. \tag{2}$$

In [1, 9], the authors showed that for any prime number $p \geq 5$

$$H_{p-1}(q) \equiv \frac{p-1}{2}(q-1) + \frac{p^2-1}{24}(1-q)^2 [p]_q \pmod{[p]_q^2}. \tag{3}$$

In [3], Glaisher proved that for any prime number $p \geq 3$,

$$q_p(2) \equiv -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{2^k}{k} \pmod{p},$$

and Skula conjectured that for any prime number $p \geq 5$,

$$q_p^2(2) \equiv -\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{2^k}{k^2} \pmod{p}.$$

In [4], Granville showed for that any prime number $p \geq 5$,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^k}{k} \equiv \frac{1 - x^p + (x - 1)^p}{p} \pmod{p}. \tag{4}$$

In [10], Sun showed that for any prime number $p \geq 3$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^k}{k^2} &\equiv \frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{1 + (x - 1)^p - x^p}{p} - \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{(1 - x)^k - 1}{k} \right) \\ &\quad + p \sum_{k=2}^{p-1} \frac{x^k}{k^2} H_{k-1} \pmod{p^2}. \end{aligned}$$

In [11], Tauraso obtained that for a positive integer α and $k = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$,

$$\left[\begin{matrix} \alpha p - 1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right]_q \equiv (-1)^k q^{\alpha p k - \binom{k+1}{2}} \left(1 - [\alpha p]_q H_k(q) \right) \pmod{[p]_q^2}. \tag{5}$$

In [7], Pan and Cao defined the q -Fermat quotient by

$$Q_p(m, q) = \frac{(q^m; q^m)_{p-1} / (q; q)_{p-1} - 1}{[p]_q},$$

where m is any nonnegative integer such that $p \nmid m$.

In [8], Pan established that for any prime number $p \geq 5$,

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \frac{q^j (-q; q)_j}{[j]_q^2} + Q_p^2(2, q) \\ &\equiv -(p - 1)Q_p(2, q)(1 - q) - \frac{(7p - 5)(p - 1)}{24} (1 - q)^2 \pmod{[p]_q}, \end{aligned}$$

and for any prime number p ,

$$q^{kp} \equiv 1 - k(1 - q)[p]_q + \binom{k}{2} (1 - q)^2 [p]_q^2 \pmod{[p]_q^3}. \tag{6}$$

In [11], Tauraso showed that for any prime number $p \geq 3$, if a, b and d are integers such that $a, d > b, b \geq 0$ and $(a, p) = 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{q^{bk}}{[ak]_q^d} &\equiv \frac{(1 - q)^d}{p^d} \left((-1)^d p \sum_{s=0}^{d-1} c_s \binom{r_0 + sp}{d} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \sum_{s=0}^d (-1)^s \binom{d}{s} \binom{sp}{2d} \right) \pmod{[p]_q}, \end{aligned}$$

where $r_0 = -b/a \pmod{p}$ such that $r_0 \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ and

$$c_s = \sum_{k=0}^s (-1)^{s-k} \binom{r_0 + kp + d - 1}{d - 1} \binom{d}{s - k}.$$

In [5], He obtained that for any prime number $p \geq 5$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{(-1)^k}{[k]_q} &\equiv -2Q_p(2, q) - \frac{(p-1)(1-q)}{2} + Q_p^2(2, q) [p]_q \\ &\quad + \left(Q_p(2, q)(1-q) + \frac{(p^2-1)(1-q)^2}{12} \right) [p]_q \pmod{[p]_q^2}. \end{aligned}$$

2. Some Congruences

In this section, firstly, the following lemma will be given for the proof of Theorem 1 .

Lemma 1. *Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime number. For all $x \in \mathbb{R}$,*

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) \equiv \frac{1}{[p]_q} \left([p]_{xq^{p-1}} - (x; q)_{p-1} \right) \pmod{[p]_q}. \tag{7}$$

Proof. By (2) and (5), we write

$$\begin{aligned} (x; q)_{p-1} &= \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} q^{\binom{k}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} p-1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_q (-x)^k \\ &\equiv \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} q^{pk - \binom{k+1}{2} + \binom{k}{2}} \left(1 - [p]_q H_k(q) \right) x^k \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} (xq^{p-1})^k - [p]_q \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) \\ &= \frac{1 - (xq^{p-1})^p}{1 - xq^{p-1}} - [p]_q \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) \pmod{[p]_q^2}. \end{aligned}$$

So, the proof is obtained. □

Lemma 2. *For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} q^k \frac{(x; q)_k - 1}{[k]_q} = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} n-1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_q \frac{(-x)^k}{[k]_q}. \tag{8}$$

Proof. From (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} q^k \frac{(x; q)_k - 1}{[k]_q} &= \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{q^k}{[k]_q} \sum_{j=1}^k (-1)^j q^{\binom{j}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} k \\ j \end{bmatrix}_q x^j \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} q^{\binom{j}{2}+j} (-x)^j \sum_{k=j}^{n-1} \frac{q^{k-j}}{[k]_q} \begin{bmatrix} k \\ j \end{bmatrix}_q \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} q^{\binom{j+1}{2}} \frac{(-x)^j}{[j]_q} \sum_{k=j}^{n-1} q^{k-j} \begin{bmatrix} k-1 \\ j-1 \end{bmatrix}_q \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} q^{\binom{j+1}{2}} \frac{(-x)^j}{[j]_q} \sum_{k=j-1}^{n-2} q^{k-(j-1)} \begin{bmatrix} k \\ j-1 \end{bmatrix}_q. \end{aligned}$$

By (1), we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} q^k \frac{(x; q)_k - 1}{[k]_q} = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} q^{\binom{j+1}{2}} \frac{(-x)^j}{[j]_q} \begin{bmatrix} n-1 \\ j \end{bmatrix}_q,$$

so, we have the proof. □

Now, we will give the q -analogue of Granville’s congruence in (4).

Theorem 1. *For all $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and a prime number $p \geq 3$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^k}{[k]_q} \equiv \frac{1 - x^p - (x; q)_p}{[p]_q} + x^p \frac{(p-1)(1-q)}{2} \pmod{[p]_q}. \tag{9}$$

Proof. Consider that

$$\begin{aligned} &x^{p-1} q^{(p-1)^2} H_{p-1}(q) \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) - \sum_{k=1}^{p-2} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{p-2} (xq^{p-1})^{k+1} H_{k+1}(q) - \sum_{k=0}^{p-2} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{p-2} (xq^{p-1})^{k+1} \left(H_k(q) + \frac{q^{k+1}}{[k+1]_q} \right) - \sum_{k=0}^{p-2} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) \\ &= (xq^{p-1}) \sum_{k=0}^{p-2} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) + \sum_{k=0}^{p-2} \frac{(xq^{p-1})^{k+1} q^{k+1}}{[k+1]_q} - \sum_{k=0}^{p-2} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (xq^{p-1} - 1) \sum_{k=0}^{p-2} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{(xq^{p-1})^k q^k}{[k]_q} \\ &= (xq^{p-1} - 1) \left(\sum_{k=0}^{p-1} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) - (xq^{p-1})^{p-1} H_{p-1}(q) \right) + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^k q^{pk}}{[k]_q}. \end{aligned}$$

From necessary rearrangements, we write

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^k q^{pk}}{[k]_q} = (1 - xq^{p-1}) \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) + xq^{p-1} (xq^{p-1})^{p-1} H_{p-1}(q).$$

Using (3) and (6), we get

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^k}{[k]_q} \equiv (1 - xq^{p-1}) \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} (xq^{p-1})^k H_k(q) + x^p \frac{p-1}{2} (q-1) \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

With the help of (6) and (7), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^k}{[k]_q} &\equiv (1 - xq^{p-1}) \frac{1}{[p]_q} \left(\frac{1 - (xq^{p-1})^p}{1 - xq^{p-1}} - (x; q)_{p-1} \right) + x^p \frac{p-1}{2} (q-1) \\ &= \frac{1 - (xq^{p-1})^p - (1 - xq^{p-1}) (x; q)_{p-1}}{[p]_q} + x^p \frac{p-1}{2} (q-1) \\ &\equiv \frac{1 - x^p - (x; q)_p}{[p]_q} + x^p \frac{(p-1)(1-q)}{2} \pmod{[p]_q}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the proof is complete. □

For example, when $x = -1$ and q^n in Theorem 1, respectively, we have that for any prime number $p \geq 3$,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{(-1)^k}{[k]_q} \equiv -2Q_p(2, q) + \frac{(p-1)(q-1)}{2} \pmod{[p]_q}[5],$$

and for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{q^{nk}}{[k]_q} \equiv -\frac{(q^n; q)_p}{[p]_q} + (1-q) \left(n + \frac{p-1}{2} \right) \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

Corollary 1. *Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime number. We have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} q^k \frac{(x; q)_k}{[k]_q} \equiv \frac{1 - x^p - (x; q)_p}{[p]_q} + (x^p - 1) \frac{(p-1)(1-q)}{2} \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

Proof. Taking p in place of n in Lemma 2 and by (5), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} q^k \frac{(x; q)_k}{[k]_q} &= \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} p-1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_q \frac{(-x)^k}{[k]_q} + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{q^k}{[k]_q} \\ &\equiv \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{(xq^p)^k}{[k]_q} + H_{p-1}(q) \pmod{[p]_q}. \end{aligned}$$

By (6) and Theorem 1, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} q^k \frac{(x; q)_k}{[k]_q} \equiv \frac{1 - x^p - (x; q)_p}{[p]_q} + x^p \frac{(p-1)(1-q)}{2} + H_{p-1}(q) \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

From (3), the desired result is given. □

For example, for any prime number $p \geq 3$, Corollary 1 is reduced as follows (see also [8] and [11]):

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} q^k \frac{(-q; q)_k}{[k]_q} \equiv \frac{2 - (-q; q)_p}{[p]_q} + p(q-1) \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

Corollary 2. *For all $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and a prime number $p \geq 3$, we have*

$$\sum_{1 \leq i \leq k \leq p-1} q^k \frac{x^i}{[i]_q} \equiv 1 - x [p]_x - (x; q)_p + x^p \frac{(p-1)(1-q)}{2} [p]_q \pmod{[p]_q^2}.$$

Proof. Observe that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{1 \leq i \leq k \leq p-1} q^k \frac{x^i}{[i]_q} &= \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^j}{[j]_q} \sum_{k=j}^{p-1} q^k \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^j}{[j]_q} \left(\frac{1 - q^p}{1 - q} - \frac{1 - q^j}{1 - q} \right) \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^k}{[k]_q} [p]_q - \sum_{j=0}^{p-1} x^j + 1. \end{aligned}$$

From Theorem 1, we have

$$\sum_{1 \leq i \leq k \leq p-1} q^k \frac{x^i}{[i]_q} \equiv 1 - x [p]_x - (x; q)_p + x^p \frac{(p-1)(1-q)}{2} [p]_q \pmod{[p]_q^2},$$

as claimed. □

References

- [1] G. E. Andrews, q -analogs of the binomial coefficient congruences of Babbage, Wolstenholme and Glaisher, *Discrete Math.* **204** (1999), 15-25.
- [2] G. E. Andrews, R. Askey and R. Roy, *Special Functions*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2000.
- [3] J.W.L. Glaisher, On the residues of the sums of the products of the first $p - 1$ numbers and their powers to modulo p^2 or p^3 , *Q. J. Math.* **31** (1900), 321-353.
- [4] A. Granville, The square of the Fermat Quotient, *Integers* **4** (2004), #A22, 3 pp.
- [5] B. He, On q -congruences involving harmonic numbers, *Ukrainian Math. J.* **69(9)** (2018), 1463-1472.
- [6] E. Lehmer, On congruences involving Bernoulli numbers and the quotients of Fermat and Wilson, *Ann. Math.* **39** (1938), 350-360.
- [7] H. Pan, H-Q. Cao, A congruence involving products of q - binomial coefficients, *J. Number Theory* **121** (2006), 224-233.
- [8] H. Pan, A q -analogue of Lehmer's congruence, *Acta Arith.* **128** (2007), 303-318.
- [9] L-L. Shi and H. Pan, A q -analogue of Wolstenholme's harmonic series congruence, *Amer. Math. Monthly* **114(6)** (2007), 529-531.
- [10] Z.H. Sun, Congruences involving Bernoulli and Euler numbers, *J. Number Theory* **128(2)** (2008), 280-312.
- [11] R. Tauraso, Some q -analogs of congruences for central binomial sums, *Colloq. Math.* **133** (2013), 133-143.
- [12] J. Wolstenholme, On certain properties of prime numbers, *Quart. J. Pure Appl. Math.* **5** (1862), 35-39.